

Duration of analgesia leave-one-out sensitivity analysis

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexamethasone

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	tau
Aliste J	10 min (-184 to 204)	0.920	177
Albrecht E	90 min (-130 to 310)	0.422	202
Chassery C	85 min (-140 to 310)	0.458	207
Rodrigues D	74 min (-91 to 240)	0.379	155
Zhang P	-3 min (-222 to 215)	0.976	192
Maagaard M	31 min (-195 to 257)	0.785	215
Pooled estimate	50 min (-140 to 239)	0.608	192

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexmedetomidine

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	tau
Hong B 2019	284 min (147 to 422)	< 0.001	84
Hong B 2021	414 min (172 to 656)	< 0.001	182
Rodrigues D	379 min (157 to 602)	< 0.001	180
Zhang P	479 min (301 to 657)	< 0.001	101
Pooled estimate	388 min (211 to 565)	< 0.001	148

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus placebo

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	Tau
Zhang P	612 min (343 to 899)	< 0.001	NA
Maagaard M	384 min (318 to 451)	< 0.001	NA
Pooled estimate	460 min (249 to 671)	< 0.001	126

Duration of motor block leave-one-out sensitivity analysis

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexamethasone

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	Tau
Aliste J	-7 min (-79 to 65)	0.848	11
Albrecht E	107 min (-66 to 280)	0.227	131
Kang RA	86 min (-111 to 282)	0.392	151
Maagaard M	79 min (-104 to 263)	0.398	152
Pooled estimate	66 min (-76 to 209)	0.363	125

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexmedetomidine: Not applicable (only 1 trial)

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus placebo:

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	Tau
Kang RA	250 min (22 to 478)	0.032	NA
Maagaard M	168 min (79 to 257)	< 0.001	NA
Pooled estimate	181 min (88 to 274)	< 0.001	24

Duration of sensory block leave-one-out sensitivity analysis

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexamethasone:

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	Tau
Aliste J	6 min (-99 to 111)	0.911	NA
Albrecht E	264 min (136 to 398)	< 0.001	NA
Pooled estimate	132 min (-112 to 376)	0.288	166

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexmedetomidine: not applicable (only 1 trial)

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus placebo: not applicable (0 trials)

Adverse events leave-one-out sensitivity analysis

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexamethasone

Omitting	RR (95% CI)	p-value	tau
Aliste J	1.00 (0.63 to 1.60)	0.987	0.30
Albrecht E	1.03 (0.67 to 1.60)	0.887	0.28
Chassery C	1.23 (0.76 to 1.99)	0.410	0.39
Rodrigues D	1.20 (0.74 to 1.95)	0.450	0.39
Zhang P	1.22 (0.79 to 1.89)	0.373	0.39
Maagaard M	1.49 (1.13 to 1.97)	0.005	0.14
Pooled estimate	1.23 (0.82 to 1.83)	0.31	0.34

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexmedetomidine

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	Tau
Hong B 2021	1.16 (0.69 to 1.98)	0.579	0.01
Rodrigues D	0.79 (0.43 to 1.46)	0.453	0.03
Zhang P	0.98 (0.60 to 1.58)	0.921	0.17
Pooled estimate	0.98 (0.64 to 1.51)	0.932	0.11

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus placebo:

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	Tau
Kang RA	0.92 (0.09 to 9.43)	0.942	1.36
Zhang P	0.50 (0.26 to 0.99)	0.047	0.13
Maagaard M	1.06 (0.16 to 6.89)	0.949	1.03
Pooled estimate	0.68 (0.18 to 2.56)	0.570	1.03

Cumulative 24-hour opioid consumption leave-one-out sensitivity analysis

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexamethasone:

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	Tau
Albrecht E	-1 mg (-6 to 5)	0.820	4
Chassery C	-1 mg (-6 to 4)	0.701	4
Kang RA	1 mg (0 to 2)	0.036	0
Maagaard M	-1 mg (-6 to 5)	0.801	4.2
Pooled estimate	0 mg (-4 to 4)	0.994	3

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexmedetomidine: not applicable (only 1 trial)

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus placebo:

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	Tau
Kang RA	-8 mg (-12 to -3)	< 0.001	NA
Maagaard M	-19 mg (-26 to -12)	< 0.001	NA
Pooled estimate	-13 mg (-24 to -2)	0.016	7

Cumulative 48-hour opioid consumption leave-one-out sensitivity analysis

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexamethasone:

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	Tau
Albrecht E	-3 mg (-13 to 8)	0.618	9
Chassery C	-4 mg (-13 to 5)	0.421	7
Zhang P	3 mg (0 to 6)	0.093	2
Maagaard M	2 mg (-12 to 9)	0.763	9
Pooled estimate	-1 mg (-9 to 6)	0.742	7

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexmedetomidine: not applicable (only 1 trial)

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus placebo:

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	Tau
Zhang P	-8 mg (-16 to 1)	0.078	NA
Maagaard M	-26 mg (-33 to -19)	< 0.001	NA
Pooled estimate	-17 mg (-35 to 0)	0.055	12

Pain 24 hours leave-one-out sensitivity analysis

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexamethasone:

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	Tau
Albrecht E	-0.7 points (-1.5 to 0.2)	0.118	0.7
Chassery C	-0.6 points (-1.4 to 0.3)	0.198	0.8
Kang RA	-0.1 points (-0.7 to 0.4)	0.628	0.3
Zhang P	-0.8 points (-1.5 to 0.0)	0.049	0.6
Maagaard M	-0.4 points (-1.3 to 0.4)	0.304	0.7
Pooled estimate	-0.5 points (-1.2 to 0.2)	0.304	0.7

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexmedetomidine:

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	Tau
Hong B 2021	-1.1 points (-1.7 to -0.5)	< 0.001	NA
Zhang P	-2.2 points (-3.7 to -0.7)	0.003	NA
Pooled estimate	-1.5 points (-2.5 to -0.4)	0.005	0.5

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus placebo:

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	Tau
Kang RA	-1.1 points (-3.1 to 1.0)	0.303	1.4
Zhang P	-2.0 points (-2.6 to -1.3)	< 0.001	0.09
Maagaard M	-0.9 points (-2.6 to 0.8)	0.285	1.2
Pooled estimate	-1.3 points (-2.6 to 0)	0.047	1.1

Pain 48 hours leave-one-out sensitivity analysis

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexamethasone:

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	Tau
Albrecht E	0 points (-0.4 to 0.3)	0.816	0.1
Chassery C	-0.1 points (0.5 to 0.2)	0.409	0.0
Zhang P	0 points (-0.6 to 0.5)	0.847	0.2
Maagaard M	0 points (-0.5 to 0.3)	0.742	0.2
Pooled estimate	0 points (-0.4 to 0.3)	0.641	0.1

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus dexmedetomidine: not applicable (only 1 trial)

Dexamethasone + dexmedetomidine versus placebo:

Omitting	MD (95% CI)	p-value	Tau
Zhang P	-0.2 points (-1.2 to 0.8)	0.704	NA
Maagaard M	-0.6 points (-0.9 to -0.1)	0.002	NA
Pooled estimate	-0.5 points (-0.9 to -0.1)	0.007	0.1

The remaining outcomes and comparisons were not applicable for leave-one-out analysis due to lack of outcome reporting.